

WP1

DMP

D1.1

NIVA

June 2024, revised October
2025

Funded by the
European Union

Technical references

Deliverable Title	Initial Data Management Plan
Project Acronym	CONTRAST
Project title	Contaminants of emerging concern: An integrated approach for assessing impacts on the marine environment.
Project Coordinator	Steven Brooks
Project Duration	48 Months (4 years)
Work Package	1
Work Package Lead	NIVA
Deliverable's DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17464753
Lead Beneficiary	NIVA
Due date	30 June 2024
Submission date	28 June 2024, revised version 09 October 2025
Authors	Sophie Mentzel, Marina Lipizer, Dag Øystein Hjermann, Samantha Martins, Steven Brooks and Viviane Girardin
Reviewed by	Kim Leirvik
Version	1.2
Version submission date	07.11.2025

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History of Changes

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	28.06.2024	Initial version.
1.1	09.10.2025	Revised version with minor text adjustments and the following changes: Better explanation of Open Access strategy within the project: Table 1: Discipline or data theme replaced with Dataset description Table 3: Data access conditions. A license was added to all data, increasing transparency that all data will be open. The column "embargo period" was removed. Embargo is exception and conditions are clarified in the text below the table. This complies with the request to clarify that data can be public but also confidential A paragraph clarifying that the other types of data generated within CONTRAST will also be made publicly available was added to the Section "Other Research Outputs"
		Correction of the links
		Addition of the link to the CONTRAST Zenodo community
1.2	07.11.2025	Restructured the document based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template , Updated document metadata (Author and Reviewer roles, and document's DOI). Guidelines for the use of the DMP added to Zenodo, with link provided in this document

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This document has been elaborated by the authors following the guidelines for data management in Horizon 2020.

Executive Summary

This document outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the CONTRAST project, as stipulated in the Grant Agreement and in accordance with EU Horizon Europe guidelines/templates. The DMP defines the project's data and outlines steps to ensure all outputs adhere to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). This initial version was developed based on current knowledge (after 6 months) and will be regularly updated throughout the project's duration.

The Data and Knowledge Management task leader will review the DMP every 6 months starting from its initial submission. Discussions with the project coordinator will determine necessary updates, which will be implemented accordingly.

This DMP provides guidelines for partners to follow and will evolve with specific information on CONTRAST datasets over time. It includes a summary of anticipated data collection, primarily through monitoring, field work, and laboratory experiments, and modelling. It also details how the project will implement the FAIR data policy using established frameworks and guidelines.

Key data management issues addressed include standardisation of (meta)data, formats, data quality control measures, and mechanisms for data and metadata identification and vocabulary.

This version (v 1.2) was revised in October 2025 following request by the project officer, changes are listed in the History of Changes table. Further updates will be included in the DMP version 2.0 (mid-term DMP), which will be delivered in month 24 (D1.2).

Abbreviations

ALLEA	All European Academies
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centre
CC-BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
CDP	Customer data platform
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CECs	Contaminants of Emerging Concern
CF	Climate and Forecast
CSV	Comma Separated Values
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DOM	Dissolved Organic Matter
EC	European Commission
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EU	European Union
GB	Gigabyte
IAF	Integrated Assessment Framework
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Re-usability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
M	Month
MB	Megabyte
MS	Milestone
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
N/A	Not Applicable
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
ODF	Open Document Format
ODV	Ocean Data View
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PIDs	Persistent Identifiers
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter
TBD	To Be Determined
UTF	Unicode Transformation Format
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WMA	World Medical Association
WP	Work Package

About the project

The Horizon Europe project, CONTRAST, will develop an integrated assessment and effect-based monitoring framework (IAF) to measure the impacts of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) on the marine environment, which will contribute to the assessment of Good Environmental/ Ecological Status for application in EU policy (i.e., Marine Strategy Framework Directive, MSFD/ Water Framework Directive, WFD). The IAF will involve chemical measurements together with biological effects endpoints optimised to detect the presence and effect of CECs in the marine environment. Chemical prioritisation schemes will identify the CECs that pose the greatest threat to marine life and select which CECs to target in the laboratory experiments, where the effects on organisms and biodiversity will be assessed. *In silico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo* bioassays will be used to determine the mechanisms of toxicity of selected CECs. Providing information on how CECs interact with organisms at environmentally relevant concentrations, and which biological effects tools should be used in the IAF to cover the range of toxicity mechanisms that CECs produce. A series of European-wide case studies will be used to test the suitability of the IAF to measure the effects of chemicals including CECs on indicator species and biodiversity. The knowledge gained from field testing and laboratory studies will form the basis for guidance documents and policy briefs on best practices for performing an IAF on CECs in the marine environment and help to provide the necessary protection of marine ecosystems.

About this DMP

This Data Management Plan (DMP) details how data will be collected, generated, processed, and stored throughout the CONTRAST project, in line with the European Commission's Open Science policy and FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It outlines the sourcing, processing, analysis, and storage of project data, the standards and methodologies adopted, and the intended audience. Data will be collected through monitoring, field work, and laboratory experiments.

The DMP also addresses ethics and intellectual property, facilitating reuse according to the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” (HE Programme Guide, 2022), while ensuring compliance with GDPR. All partners are responsible for ensuring their data conforms to the DMP and applicable national requirements.

This DMP will be iteratively refined through deliverables at M24 (D1.2) and M45 (D1.3), keeping it up-to-date, flexible, and aligned with project objectives. The initial version was developed with input from all partners, including a table summarizing datasets per work package/task and key characteristics. The final version will be created and maintained in the [ARGOS online DMP tool](#). ARGOS produces a standardised, machine-actionable DMP—enhancing the interoperability of project data—and provides guidance and templates aligned with funding agency requirements. By using ARGOS, the consortium ensures efficient, transparent, and reproducible data management, contributing to FAIR compliance and advancing open science and research data stewardship (Papadopoulou et al., 2023).

Data summary

This section provides an overview of the datasets planned in CONTRAST. It describes their expected origin, formats, and methods of generation or collection, as well as allocation across Work Packages (WPs). The primary purpose and utility is highlighted, explaining how the data support the project objectives and may be reused. Information on repositories or storage locations is provided to ensure secure preservation and controlled access, following FAIR principles and, where applicable, standardised metadata and persistent identifiers. Additional datasets and details will be included in future updates of the DMP, as applicable.

Purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project

The CONTRAST project collects and generates data to identify and prioritise contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) that pose risks to marine ecosystems. This includes data on the occurrence, transport, and fate of CECs in the marine environment, as well as their biological and ecological effects on marine organisms. The project also gathers information through laboratory experiments, modelling, and field case studies to develop and validate an integrated assessment framework.

This data collection directly supports the project's objectives: understanding how CECs behave and impact marine life, determining their interactions with climate change, and creating tools and guidance for monitoring and policy implementation. Overall, data generation in CONTRAST is central to achieving its goal of improving marine environmental protection and ensuring good environmental status in European seas.

Use of existing data

CONTRAST may use existing datasets to complement newly generated data. Relevant chemical monitoring data, ecotoxicological databases, and environmental status assessments from previous EU and national projects, research infrastructures, and monitoring programmes might be integrated where appropriate. Re-use of such data helps to strengthen the project's analyses, support chemical prioritisation, and enhance the robustness of the integrated assessment framework. All reused datasets will be properly cited and credited to their original sources, ensuring transparency, traceability, and alignment with FAIR data principles.

Expected data size

The exact size of the data to be generated or re-used is not yet determined. However, the size of each dataset will be specified once available and documented accordingly in the DMP.

Data origin/provenance

A high-level summary of the currently expected datasets from the different WPs are summarized in **Error! Reference source not found.** This list will be updated during the

lifetime of this DMP, and it might be subdivided into datasets from specific deliverables. For this initial version it is indicative of important datasets to be produced.

Data utility

The data generated and compiled within CONTRAST will have long-term value beyond the duration of the project. The integrated datasets will provide scientific basis for improving the assessment and management of CECs in marine environments, supporting European and national monitoring initiatives and policy implementation under the MSFD and other relevant EU legislation. Furthermore, by ensuring data are FAIR, the project will facilitate their use by the wider scientific, regulatory and policy communities, contributing to future research, innovation, and evidence-based decision-making for marine environmental protection.

Overview of expected datasets

Table 1 provides an overview of the data anticipated to be collected or generated by CONTRAST partners. It includes information on the data's source, discipline, associated task, and the partner responsible for its management. This table serves as an introduction to the datasets that are utilised within the project. Furthermore, this table contains some details on the data set format, properties and dimension.

Table 1 General description of expected data, volume and format generated during the execution of the CONTRAST project.

Partner acronym	WP	Task	Dataset description	Data type: field, laboratory, model data, maps etc.	Expected data format	Quantitative, only qualitative, both, or other data procedure	Data readiness	Dataset general dimension (GIGA, TERA byte, etc.)
DEFRA / CEFAS	2, 3, 5	2.2; 2.5; 5.1; 5.3	Contaminant/substance concentration (any matrix)	<i>In situ</i> data (monitoring)	Excel	Both quantitative and qualitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD ¹
DEFRA / CEFAS	4	4.1	Biodiversity, contaminant effects-impacts	methods, species lists	Excel	Qualitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
DEFRA / CEFAS	3,4,5,7	3.2,3.3, 4.3,5.3, 7.2	Bioassays & contaminant biological impact	<i>In situ</i> data (monitoring)/ <i>In vitro</i>	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
DEFRA / CEFAS	5	5.4	Contaminant concentration and Physical Oceanography	Model outputs	NetCDF	Quantitative	Preliminary processing	TBC ² (GB or TB)
HCMR	2, 3, 5		Contaminant/substance concentration (any matrix)/bioassays	<i>In situ</i> data, <i>In vitro</i> experiments	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
HCMR	2, 3, 5		Physical oceanography	<i>In situ</i> data (monitoring)	csv	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
IEO-CSIC	2, 3, 5		Bioassays & contaminant biological impact; Contaminants	<i>In vivo</i> laboratory, <i>In situ</i>	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
IFREMER	5	5.1; 5.2	Contaminant/substance concentration (any matrix)	<i>In situ</i> data (monitoring)	Excel	Quantitative	Raw data	MB
IFREMER	5	5.2	Bioassays & contaminant biological impact	<i>In situ</i> data (monitoring)	Excel	Quantitative	Raw data	MB
IFREMER	3	3.2, 3.3, 5.2, 5.3	Bioassays & contaminant biological impact/omics data	<i>In vitro</i> experiments/ <i>In vivo</i> laboratory/ <i>In situ</i> data	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
IFREMER	3	3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 5.3	Bioassays & contaminant biological impact	<i>In vitro</i> experiments/ <i>In</i>	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD

¹ TBD – to be decided/ determined.

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Partner acronym	WP	Task	Dataset description	Data type: field, laboratory, model data, maps etc.	Expected data format	Quantitative, only qualitative, both, or other data procedure	Data readiness	Dataset general dimension (GIGA, TERA byte, etc.)
				<i>vivo</i> laboratory/ <i>In situ</i> data				
ILVO	2, 5	2.2; 2.4; 2.5; 5.1; 5.3	Contaminant/substance concentration (any matrix)	<i>In situ</i> data (monitoring)	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
ILVO	4	4.2	Genomics or other omics data	Microcosm	csv	Both quantitative and qualitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TBD
IMR	2, 3, 4, 5, 6		Contaminant/substance concentration (any matrix)	Field, lab, mesocosm	csv	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	MB
IMR	3, 4, 5, 7		Bioassays & contaminant biological impact		csv	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	MB
IMR	3, 4, 5		Genomics or other omics data		csv	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	GB
IFREMER	3		Bioassays & contaminant biological impact	<i>In vitro</i> - and <i>In vivo</i> experiments, mesocosm	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	Max GB
NIVA	3,4,5	3.2; 3.3, 3.4; 4.3; 5.3	Bioassays & contaminant biological impact	<i>In vitro</i> - and <i>In vivo</i> experiments, <i>In situ</i> (monitoring data)	Excel	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	TERA byte (OMICS)
NIVA	6	6.2	Maps of estimated cumulative effects	Assessment results (tool output)	tif/xyz/csv	Quantitative	Advanced processing (ready to use data)	MB
NIVA	2	2.3	Modelling vertical distribution of selected CECs in the water column and marine sediments	Model outputs	NetCDF	Quantitative	Raw model output	GB
UGOT	7	7.2, 7.3	Proficiency testing	Biomarker and chemical	Excel	Both quantitative and qualitative	TBD	MB

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Partner acronym	WP	Task	Dataset description	Data type: field, laboratory, model data, maps etc.	Expected data format	Quantitative, only qualitative, both, or other data procedure	Data readiness	Dataset general dimension (GIGA, TERA byte, etc.)
				concentration data				

FAIR data

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To ensure that project data are findable and accessible, datasets will be described using consolidated metadata standards aligned with established European marine data infrastructures. CONTRAST will follow the conventions used within the SeaDataNet and those adopted by EMODnet Chemistry. These standards apply especially to data generated in the case studies (e.g., chemical concentrations and biological effects) that will feed into EMODnet and related EU infrastructures.

This approach will facilitate metadata sharing, discovery, and access under pre-defined data access conditions via EMODnet. Metadata standards include the use of common vocabularies to code parameters such as keywords, scientific disciplines, and measured variables.

To promote data interoperability, consolidated metadata, data standards, and controlled vocabularies will be adopted wherever possible, considering EU data infrastructures such as SeaDataNet and EMODnet (for *in-situ* contaminant concentrations and physical oceanography), ICES (for biological effects), and global systems such as OBIS (for biodiversity data). Open data policies will be encouraged; however, some data typologies may require a temporary embargo period to ensure scientific integrity and publication rights.

Table 2- Metadata fields for datasets

Metadata Field	Description	Reference Standard/Vocabulary
Dataset title	Descriptive title of the dataset	Dublin Core / DataCite
Creators / Contributors	Names, affiliations, ORCID identifiers of data producers	Dublin Core / ORCID
Abstract / Description	Short summary of dataset content and purpose	Dublin Core
Keywords / Parameters	Controlled terms describing variables (e.g., contaminant type, species, parameter code)	SeaDataNet, EMODnet, ICES vocabularies
Geographical coverage	Bounding box or station coordinates, region names	ISO 19115 / SeaDataNet
Temporal coverage	Start and end dates of sampling or observation period	ISO 8601
Data type and format	Laboratory, field, model, map, etc.	Project-defined / SeaDataNet
Methodology / Protocol	Reference to sampling or analytical procedures	ICES / EMODnet
License	Usage rights (e.g., CC-BY 4.0, CC0)	OpenAIRE / Creative Commons

Access level	Open, restricted, or embargoed, with justification	FAIR principles
Persistent Identifier (PID)	DOI automatically assigned by Zenodo	DataCite
Version and update date	Dataset version number and date of last update	ISO 19115
Funding information	Horizon Europe Grant Agreement number and project acronym	DataCite

Persistent and unique identifiers

Many of the data repositories under consideration support unique identifiers and focus for publication data will be on repositories that support DOI generation. During project execution the use of unique identifiers is good way to ensure traceability of shared data.

Naming conventions

To support a harmonised and organised approach to manage datasets, participants are encouraged to use the following rules to name the files:

WPnumber_TaskNumber_PartnerAcronym_Easy-to-understand-content_date

Example:

WP5_T5.3_NIVA_Bioassay-CampaignXX-sediment_14.03.2024

The file naming standardisation was part of milestone 2 (MS2): Shared platform for data submission and sharing within CONTRAST, delivered on month 3.

Versioning

Version control will be applied to ensure that updates and changes to datasets are tracked and documented over time. The approach will depend on the data type, responsible data owner, and repository requirements. Where applicable, metadata will record the dataset version, creation and modification dates, and links between related versions to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) will be used whenever supported by the selected repository to guarantee long-term findability and citation. Zenodo, SeaDataNet, EMODnet, and ICES support, or are in the process of implementing, DOI or equivalent PID assignment for published datasets and data products. For data deposited in Zenodo, a DOI is automatically minted upon publication, including a versioned DOI structure. For deposits in other infrastructures, existing PID and citation mechanisms will be followed, and, where direct DOI assignment is not yet available, internal or repository-specific unique identifiers will be used and documented in the metadata.

All datasets will include sufficient metadata to enable clear identification of their origin, version, and relation to other project outputs. The chosen repositories provide reliable, long-

term preservation and ensure that data remains accessible and citable beyond the project's lifetime.

Making data accessible

For datasets that do not fall within the scope of EMODnet, ICES, or OBIS, the consortium will deposit finalised data in the [CONTRAST community on Zenodo](https://nivanorge.github.io/contrast/), an open-access repository developed by CERN under the OpenAIRE initiative. Zenodo is widely used for Horizon Europe projects and ensures compliance with FAIR and Open Science principles. Guidelines on how to upload data to our Zenodo community are available at

<https://nivanorge.github.io/contrast/>

Given the heterogeneity of data types produced within CONTRAST, some large-scale datasets (e.g., genomic or omics data) may not be suitable for Zenodo due to size limitations or ingestion speed. In such cases, more specialised international repositories will be used. Code and model developments will be stored in GitHub, ensuring transparency and collaborative access.

Datasets and outputs suitable for Zenodo will become publicly accessible once the related scientific publication has been released, a deliverable has been approved for public dissemination, or at the end of the project, in accordance with the consortium's open data policy.

Making data interoperable

To make publication and project data interoperable, CONTRAST will prioritise the use of accessible, non-proprietary, and broadly accepted formats. Wherever possible, tabular data will be provided in CSV format using standardized character encoding (e.g. UTF-8) and metadata. When relevant, disciplinary or community standards (e.g. ISO 19115 for geospatial metadata, CF conventions for NetCDF files, or DataCite metadata for datasets) will be applied to enhance interoperability and long-term reuse.

Table 3 below provides an overview of the **key anticipated digital outputs** that will be generated for communication, dissemination, and reuse within and beyond the project. The formats indicated are preliminary and may be adjusted to align with repository requirements and evolving best practices.

Table 3 List of the key anticipated digital outputs for communication and dissemination in the project.

Main deliverable type: Data (datasets, microdata)

Type of data	Characteristics	Possible formats
Chemical and physicochemical data	Concentration of CECs and legacy contaminants in different matrices, physicochemical properties such as temperature, salinity, oxygen, suspended particle matter (SPM), dissolved organic matter (DOM)	Recommended: .csv or .tab Accepted: .xls or .xlsx

Biological Data	Information regarding living organisms, encompassing genomics (other omics data), physiological parameters, and other related aspects, e.g. field, lab, mesocosm	Recommended: .csv or .tab Accepted: .xls or .xlsx
Computational Data	Data produced by computer simulations, modelling, algorithms, or software applications, e.g., model outputs	Recommended: NetCDF-CF, GitHub repository uploaded on Zenodo
Main deliverable type: Reports/ other documents		
Type of data	Characteristics	Possible formats
Reports	Scientific reports, workshop abstracts, briefs for policy makers, internal documents and similar	Recommended: Open document format (.odf) Accepted: .pdf, .html, .docx, .xlsx, .rtf

Re-use of data (licensing)

CONTRAST's recommendation is to attach a Commons License (CC BY or CC0) to deposited publication data to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and especially disseminate our results.

Document and data internal storage

As part of the MS2: Shared platform for data submission and sharing within CONTRAST, the data management team (WP1, WP6) together with the consortium have decided that the Microsoft Teams will serve as the internal platform for collecting and storing work-in-progress data generated within the CONTRAST project.

Given the heterogeneous nature of the data produced, meticulous attention is necessary to ensure accurate collection of datasets. Through collaboration with all project partners, an inventory of data typologies has been conducted, leading to the proposal of the following folder architecture to organise various data types.

Figure 1 Overview File storage folder on the Microsoft Teams channel.

File uploading

Files should be uploaded to the appropriate sub-folder corresponding to their respective data type. For instance, data pertaining to contaminant concentrations measured in sediment should be uploaded to the designated sub-folder. If uploading the data is not a practical option (e.g. in the case of very large datasets, like omics data), the sub-folder should contain links to where the data set can be found. Instructions to upload data on the platform are provided in the guidelines available in the Teams folder.

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Table 4 Overview of the data storage, repositories, data handling and access and embargo periods of the produced data sets in the CONTRAST project.

Partner acronym	WP	Task	Data storage (highest management system)	Institute data repository available (URL Data Access provided)	Data handled by a National Data Centres listed?	Use of metadata standards	Use data standards, provide details	Data contributed to European Marine Infrastructure, provided details	Providing mapping to more commonly used ontologies	Data access conditions	Assigned persistent identifier (e.g. doi) to the dataset
DEFRA / CEFAS	2, 3, 5	2.2; 2.5; 5.1; 5.3	Institute database		None	N/A ²	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
DEFRA / CEFAS	4	4.1	Institute database	CEFAS cdp, Azure	NA	NA	NA	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
DEFRA / CEFAS	3,4,5,7	3.2,3.3,4.3,5.3,7.2	Institute database	CEFAS cdp, MERMAN	BODC	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
DEFRA / CEFAS	5	5.4	High performance computing archives		None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
HCMR	2, 3, 5		EU or global data infrastructure (e.g. ICES, EMODnet)	https://hnodc.hcmr.gr	HCMR-NODC	SeaData Net	ODV	EMODNet	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
HCMR	2, 3, 5		EU or global data infrastructure (e.g. ICES, EMODnet)	https://hnodc.hcmr.gr	HCMR-NODC	SeaData Net	ODV	EMODNet	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IEO-CSIC	2, 3, 5		EU or global data infrastructure (e.g. ICES, EMODnet,)		CSIC-NODC	N/A	TBD	TBD	TBD	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IFREMER	5	5.1; 5.2	Files on PC ³		EMBL	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IFREMER	5	5.2	Files on PC		None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IFREMER	3	3.2, 3.3, 5.2, 5.3	Files on PC		TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
ILVO	4	4.2	Institute database		TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	CC BY 4.0	On publishing

² N/A – Not applicable

³ PC - frequently backed up through institution.

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Partner acronym	WP	Task	Data storage (highest management system)	Institute data repository available (URL Data Access provided)	Data handled by a National Data Centres listed?	Use of metadata standards	Use data standards, provide details	Data contributed to European Marine Infrastructure, provided details	Providing mapping to more commonly used ontologies	Data access conditions	Assigned persistent identifier (e.g. doi) to the dataset
ILVO	2, 5	2.2; 2.4; 2.5; 5.1; 5.3	EU or global data infrastructure (e.g. ICES, EMODnet,)		Belgium-NODC	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IMR	2, 3, 4, 5, 6		Institute database	http://metadata.nmdc.no/UserInterface/#/	IMR-NODC	SeaData Net	TBD	TBD	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IMR	3, 4, 5, 7		Institute database	http://metadata.nmdc.no/UserInterface/#/	IMR-NODC	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IMR	3, 4, 5		Institute database	http://metadata.nmdc.no/UserInterface/#/	IMR-NODC	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
IFREMER	3		Institute database	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
NIVA	3,4,5	3.2; 3.3, 3.4; 4.3; 5.3	Institute database		None	No			Yes	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
NIVA	6	6.2	NIVA cloud infrastructure	None	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	On publishing
NIVA	2	2.3	Institute database		None	Yes	Yes	TBD	Yes	CC BY 4.0	On publishing

Data management platform - ARGOS

The CONTRAST project has selected the ARGOS Data Management platform (<https://argos.openaire.eu/home>) as the tool for developing the final version of the project's DMP.

ARGOS is the chosen tool because it directly fulfills EU Horizon requirements and operationalizes our commitment to FAIR data principles:

- **Horizon Compliance & Machine-Actionability:** ARGOS generates a machine-actionable DMP, structured to align with current funder standards. This structured format inherently supports the Interoperability principle, moving beyond the limitations of a static text document (Papadopoulou et al. 2023).
- **FAIR Integration:** The platform integrates with Zenodo, enabling the automatic linking of the DMP to project datasets, metadata, and assigned DOIs. This capability directly improves the findability and accessibility of the project data.
- **Governance:** ARGOS provides the required templates and workflows to document data processes, assign necessary metadata, and maintain data governance throughout the project lifecycle.

Other research outputs

In addition to the data specified in Table 1, other types of data will be produced within CONTRAST (Table 5). All data will follow the same open access strategy as described in the previous sections and will be made openly available in Zenodo or other appropriate repositories.

Table 5 Other information typologies producing documents and reports

Partner acronym	WP	Task	Task name	Output
ILVO	2	2.1	Identification of CECs relevant for the marine environment applying an optimised prioritisation scheme	Report
IMR	3	3.1	Selection of species and biomarkers	Report
IFREMER	6	6.1	Analysing, harmonising, and optimising existing integrated assessment frameworks	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

OGS	6	6.3	Enabling ease of data transfer of biological effects assessments to European data repositories	DATA — datasets, microdata, etc. (D6.2), Report (D6.6)
UGOT	7	7.1	Training workshops	training, video production
SHIRE	8	8.1	Education and outreach to the next generation	DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc
NIVA	8	8.2	Advising policy makers at the EU level	Workshop, policy briefs
NIVA	8	8.3	Commonly used tools for dissemination results from CONTRAST	Popular science publications

Allocation of Resources

We have allocated specific resources to ensure proper data management throughout the project. This includes budget provisions for data storage, processing, and open-access publishing fees. Long-term data preservation will be covered under the project's Open Science budget. The project provides secure storage infrastructure, and dedicated data manager, along with dataset responsible that will oversee compliance with FAIR principles and DMP implementation. If additional costs arise, we will explore institutional support or relevant funding mechanisms.

Data security

All project data will be stored on secure institutional servers with controlled access. If any sensitive or personal data are generated, it will be encrypted and handled in full compliance with GDPR and institutional policies. Access will be restricted to authorized team members, with authentication and logging measures in place to ensure security. Regular backups will be maintained in multiple locations to prevent data loss. If cloud storage is used, it will be limited to providers that fully comply with EU data protection regulations.

Ethical principles under Horizon Europe

Ethics are an integral part of research and of Horizon Europe projects. The ethical requirements under Horizon Europe are anchored in the *Horizon Europe Framework*

Programme [Regulation \(EU\) 2021/695 of 28 April 2021](#), as amended and consolidated on 1 March 2024. Articles 18 and 19 define the provisions regarding eligible actions and the ethical principles governing research.

CONTRAST follows existing EU and national regulations as well as internationally recognised ethical standards, including:

- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, ALLEA (2023),
- The Declaration of Helsinki, WMA (2024),
- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (and its Supplementary Protocols), in accordance with Article 19(1) of the HE Framework Programme Regulation, and
- The Convention on Biological Diversity.

All project activities will comply with these ethical principles and relevant legislation, including environmental protection laws, permits for marine sampling, and regulations for the safe handling and disposal of hazardous substances. Any data collected will follow the FAIR principles and respect confidentiality and privacy requirements where applicable, including the responsible reporting of sensitive environmental data.

Ethical compliance will be ensured through internal project monitoring, adherence to national and EU legislation, and, where necessary, submission to relevant ethics review boards or competent authorities.

Other issues

At this stage, we do not anticipate any legal, ethical, or technical issues affecting data management. However, should any challenges arise, we will address them in consultation with institutional and funding body representatives. The DMP will be treated as a living document, updated as needed to reflect any changes in project scope, new policies, or unforeseen developments.

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Appendix

Overview of the work packages (WP), tasks, deliverables (D) and milestones (MS) of the CONTRAST project

WP	Task n.	Task name	Timeline	Lead	Participants	D	MS
1	1.1	Project communication and project work plan	1-48	NIVA	All partners		MS1
1	1.2	Appointment of SAB and stakeholder committee	1-6	NIVA	All partners		MS5
1	1.3	Administrative, financial and legal project management	1-48	NIVA	All partners	D1.1, D1.2, D1.3	
1	1.4	Project management	1-48	NIVA	All partners		
2	2.1	Identification of CECs relevant for the marine environment applying an optimised prioritisation scheme	1-19	ILVO	NIVA, DEFRA, IEO-CSISC, IFREMER, HCMR, OGS	D2.1, D2.2	MS6
2	2.2	Harmonised analysis methods for CECs in the marine environment	2-15	ILVO	NIVA, DEFRA, IEO-CSIC, IMR, HCMR, IFREMER, IMR		MS12
2	2.3	Modelling vertical distribution of selected CECs in the water column and marine sediments	7-17	NIVA	DEFRA, IFREMER, IMR	D2.3	MS13
2	2.4	Understanding the interactions between CECs and climate change factors	13-21	IEO-CSIC	NIVA, ILVO	D2.4	
2	2.5	Suspect and nontarget screening approaches for detecting prioritised CECs in the marine environment	15-36	DEFRA/CEFAS	ILVO, NIVA, IEO-CSIC, HCMR, IFREMER, IMR	Contribute to D5.1, D5.2, D5.3	
3	3.1	Selection of species and biomarkers	2-12	IMR	NIVA, IEO-CSIC, IFREMER, DEFRA, UGOT		MS10
3	3.2	Biotransformation, toxicity and mechanisms of action of CECs in marine organisms	5-21	IFREMER	IMR, NIVA, DEFRA, ILVO, UGOT	D3.1	
3	3.3	Development and optimisation of biomarkers for CECs monitoring	6-25	NIVA	IEO-CSIC, IFREMER, DEFRA,	D3.2	MS15

					UGOT, IMR, HCMR, ILVO		
3	3.4	Interactions between Global Change factors and effects of CECs	18-30	IEO-CSIC	NIVA, IMR, IFREMER, UGOT, HCMR, DEFRA	D3.3	
4	4.1	Establishing methods and reference materials	2-9	DEFRA	ILVO, IMR	D4.1	MS7
4	4.2	Effects of CECs on sediment biodiversity	9-35	UGOT	IMR, DEFRA, IFREMER, NIVA, ILVO	D4.2	
4	4.3	Effects of CECs on pelagic biodiversity	14-24	NIVA	NIVA, IMR, DEFRA, UGOT		
4	4.4	Simultaneous effects on biodiversity and biomarker responses	26-34	IMR	DEFRA, IFREMER, NIVA, ILVO, UGOT	D4.3	
5	5.1	Sediment map: Relationship between chemical contamination in European coastal sediments and benthic diversity (aligned with TREC expedition and knowledge)	4-37	IFREMER	IEO-CSIC, NIVA, DEFRA, IFREMER, ILVO, IMR, HCMR, OGS	D5.1, D5.4	MS4, MS8
5	5.2	Deep sea map: Exploration of chemical contamination fate and effects in deep sea environments (aligned with national monitoring expedition and knowledge)	12-34	IEO-CSIC	IFREMER, HCMR, NIVA, DEFRA, ILVO, IMR, OGS	D5.3	MS9, MS16
5	5.3	Application of the IAF across coastal areas in European Seas	15-38	NIVA	IEO-CSIC, DEFRA, IFREMER, ILVO, IMR, HCMR, OGS, UGOT	D5.2, D5.6	MS14, MS17, MS19
5	5.4	Modelling CEC circulation and fate	25-38	DEFRA/ CEFAS	NIVA, HCMR, IMR	D5.5	MS18
6	6.1	Analysing, harmonising and optimising existing integrated assessment frameworks	6-47	IFREMER	NIVA, IEO-CSIC, IMR, ILVO	D6.4, D6.5	MS11
6	6.2	Integrated (cumulative) ecological effects assessment	29-44	NIVA	HCMR, IFREMER, OGS, IMR	D6.6	
6	6.3	Enabling ease of data transfer of biological effects assessments to European data repositories	1-48	OGS	NIVA, DEFRA, IFREMER, ILVO, IEO-CSIC, IMR, HCMR	D6.1, D6.2, D6.3, D6.8	MS2
6	6.4	Best practices for integrated assessment	36-48	NIVA	All partners	D6.7, D6.9	

framework for monitoring of CECs in European seas							
7	7.1	Training workshops	10-20	UGOT	NIVA, DEFRA, IEO-CSIC, HCMR, IFREMER, IMR, ILVO	D7.2, D7.3	
7	7.2	Proficiency testing for biomarkers	7-14	DEFRA/CEFAS	NIVA, IEO-CSIC, HCMR, IFREMER, UGOT, IMR, ILVO	D7.1	
7	7.3	Proficiency tests for chemical analysis	25-31	ILVO	NIVA, DEFRA, IEO-CSIC, HCMR, IFREMER, UGOT, IMR	D7.4	
8	8.1	Education and outreach to the next generation	1-48	SHIRE	NIVA	D8.3	
8	8.2	Advising policy makers at the EU level	15-46	NIVA	SHIRE, IFREMER	D8.5, D8.6	
8	8.3	Commonly used tools for dissemination results from CONTRAST	1-48	NIVA	All partners	D8.1, D8.2, D8.4, D8.7	MS3

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